

Accelerator & training concept

Deliverable 2.1

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IMPETUS

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Summary

In IMPETUS, 125 citizen science initiatives (CSIs) are supported, through a comprehensive training and mentoring programme (Accelerator), to develop and maximise their scientific, social, economic, democratic, and environmental impacts towards the Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs) and the Green Deal targets. These CSIs are divided into 3 cohorts, 2023-2024-2025. The Accelerator will support both new CSIs “kickstarting projects” (100) and already existing ones “Sustaining projects” (25).

This deliverable describes the IMPETUS Accelerator approach, objectives and logic and how its implementation is planned.

The Accelerator is coordinated by Science for Change (WP2 leader) and aims at setting up an impact-driven citizen science program to support each CSI cohort.

The specific objectives of the Accelerator are to:

- Define activities, key performance indicators (KPIs) and milestones with CSIs, to be implemented and evaluated during the accelerator program according to their specific needs.
- Establish a mentoring board and assign suitable mentors to CSIs supporting them in the development of their project.
- Provide tailored training, guidance, and support for CSIs to overcome barriers for citizen science challenges.
- Foster CSIs to be more open, inclusive and impactful.
- Support CSIs in establishing linkage between citizen science and quadruple-helix stakeholders to maximise impact.
- Create a citizen science community for peer-learning and networking in and between cohorts.
- Expand and consolidate the network of CSI to help position Europe as a global leader in citizen science

The first edition of the IMPETUS Accelerator (2023), will serve as a pilot for the following editions: procedure and content developed in this edition will be evaluated at the end of the year in order to incorporate improvements for the following editions (2024-2025); therefore, in the following editions there may be slight changes to what is contained in this deliverable.

The Accelerator is divided in two main phases: 1) the negotiation phase, in which the CSIs will draft a Work Plan reflecting what activities they will carry out to implement their project during the Accelerator and how they will cover and materialise different relevant aspects of citizen science (e.g. ethical issues, open data, inclusiveness, etc.). To do this they will be supported by their assigned mentors and a full week training event (bootcamp). Once the Work Plans are evaluated and validated by the IMPETUS consortium, the CSIs will officially enter 2) the Accelerator, period in which the CSIs will have to execute their planned activities; during this phase they will be provided with specific trainings, adequate to the needs of each cohort, and mentoring.

The mentors are experts in different aspects of citizen science who will help the CSIs and provide guidance for the correct execution of their activities during the Accelerator. Mentors can also be required to provide training based on their expertise if deemed necessary.

In each Accelerator edition, the performance of the CSIs will be evaluated through a monitoring procedure (mid-term and final), to ensure the achievement of their objectives, KPIs and expected impacts. Mentors will also be monitored to ensure the correct performance of their work.

At the end of each Accelerator edition, it is expected to achieve open, inclusive and impactful CSIs that contribute to UN SDGs and Green Deal targets.

Accelerator concept and outline

The IMPETUS Accelerator is a 7-month intensive training and mentoring programme to support CSIs to develop their activities in an impactful way and thus contributing to tackling the greatest challenges of our times, especially contributing to the Green Deal and the UN SDGs. The IMPETUS Accelerator will support a total of 125 CSIs, with a goal for them to become self-sustaining in the long-term and more open, inclusive and impactful. It is implemented during 3 consecutive years (annual Open Calls, 2023, 2024 and 2025). The Accelerator will support both new CSIs “kickstarting projects” (100) and already existing ones “Sustaining projects” (25) with the aim of assuring their continuation and, possibly, scaling up.

During each Accelerator edition, all CSI teams will have access to a set of services, focused to the needs of each cohort, including:

- Intensive training at the start of the Accelerator (Bootcamp) on: project design, EDI (Equity, diversity, Inclusivity), engagement & communication strategies, policy, data management and preservation, ethical aspects and impact assessment;
- Training during the whole Accelerator, covering specific needs on knowledge & skills;
- Online mentoring during project execution;
- Promotion via IMPETUS website and on social media, as well as presentation opportunities at the IMPETUS conference and other related events;
- Peer learning opportunities facilitated through workshops and online tools.
- Networking, within and between pilot cohorts, through the IMPETUS Aperitives, creating bridges with external communities of interest.

IMPETUS will work with CSIs to understand their situation and challenges and support them in addressing them. Each Accelerator edition is divided in phases as follows:

Figure 1: IMPETUS Accelerator outline

Negotiation phase (April - June)

During the evaluation process of the applicants to the call, a certain number of projects are admitted to enter the negotiation phase with the IMPETUS Consortium and 5 CSIs remain on the reserve list. Specifically, in 2023, IMPETUS will support 35 CSIs (30 kickstarting and 5 sustaining).

The objective of the negotiation phase is fulfilling the legal requirements between the IMPETUS consortium and every selected CSI of the call. The negotiation phase precedes the CSIs official involvement in the project, which is formalised with the signature of the subgrantee agreement in June.

To be able to enter the Accelerator programme and sign the subgrantee agreement, it is mandatory for the CSIs to attend a minimum of 80% of the bootcamp hours in May. If any of the CSIs do not pass the bootcamp, a reallocation has to be made by inviting CSIs from the reserve list to join the Accelerator.

Negotiations start mid-April and must finish by mid-June. If they are a CSI of the reserve list, they will be notified of their entry into this process after the bootcamp.

Funds are transferred to the projects in two stages – 50% at the beginning of the project, and the remaining 50% at the end after successfully implementing the projects.

For the signature of their contract, the CSIs need to have the following **project documents** completed and validated by their mentor:

1. A well-defined Work Plan + Data & Ethics document (hereinafter referred to as "Work Plan") for the Accelerator period (6 months) and beyond (optional): in these documents they define and agree with IMPETUS, among others, milestones and Key Performance Indicators for their activities.
2. A detailed budget, showing how they will use the financial resources allocated to them.

To pass the negotiation phase, the CSIs have to complete the following steps:

- **Due diligence checks (April-May) (Zabala):** these checks are performed to verify the legal status of the applicants.
- **Pre-questionnaire on knowledge & training needs (April) (T6 Ecosystems):** In order to define tailored made training and to be able to evaluate the success of the Accelerator, IMPETUS will ask the CSIs to fill in a preliminary questionnaire about knowledge, skills and needs. If they are a CSI of the reserve list, they will receive this pre-questionnaire on the official communication email (May).
- **Mentor assignment (May):** the IMPETUS consortium will assign the projects a specific mentor, taking into account their specific needs, who will accompany them throughout the preparation of their project documents and the Accelerator.
- **Creation of a space on the Moodle platform (May):** we chose Moodle (an Open Source software widely used in educational contexts) as our main platform where CSIs and mentors can download all the documentation related to the project (which will be uploaded by Science for Change at the appropriate time) and upload the documents requested by IMPETUS. Each CSI-mentor will have their own space to which only they and Science for Change will have access. At the beginning of the process, in Moodle they will find the templates of the project documents, a "Guide for CSIs" (in which all the details of the Accelerator are explained) and a template of meeting minutes.
- **Creation of a communication channel between CSIs (Slack or similar) (May):** to facilitate the exchange and collaboration between CSIs, IMPETUS consortium will create a dedicated agile communication channel.
- **Bootcamp (May):** before signing the contract in June, the projects have to start working on their project documents, which both mentors and CSIs will find hosted in Moodle. As part of the negotiations, once they have prepared their preliminary documents, IMPETUS will host a

full week training event that they will need to attend (bootcamp). The objective is to deepen their understanding of the most relevant citizen science topics and this will help them to perfect their plan for their citizen science project.

If a CSI from the reserve list is incorporated at this stage, they will not be able to attend the bootcamp because their work with IMPETUS will start right after. However, they will be provided with the materials and recordings of the sessions so that they can use them to work on their plan.

- **Agreement on Work Plan + Data & Ethics document and budget (June):** After the bootcamp, the CSIs have one more week to finalise the Work Plan details and submit their final project documents. With these documents, they and IMPETUS agree on activities and success criteria. IMPETUS will also assess the costs associated with their project to ensure they are eligible. The mentor has to be available to go through this process with them and answer any questions they may have.

The CSIs have to have their project documents completed, validated by their mentor and uploaded on the Moodle platform on a specific date (June). The IMPETUS consortium will evaluate them. If they are approved, the CSI will start the process for signing the contract with IMPETUS and receiving the first payment.

If they are a CSI of the reserve list, they will have two weeks to finetune their project documents (May – June). The CSIs have to have their project documents completed, validated by their mentor and uploaded on the Moodle platform one week later. The IMPETUS consortium will evaluate them. If they are approved, they will start the process for signing the contract and receiving the first payment.

The IMPETUS Accelerator (June - December)

CSIs who reach this stage of the process are formally accepted into the six-month Accelerator between June and December. The IMPETUS Accelerator will provide selected pilots with resources and training.

The IMPETUS consortium will provide, specifically:

- **5 Accelerator trainings:** 5 training sessions (1.5 hours each) will be given to cover the needs expressed by them in the pre-questionnaire.

- **IMPETUS Aperitives:** 2 Aperitives (1,5 hours each) will be held to facilitate peer-learning and networking within and between pilot cohorts
- **Monthly update calls with mentors:** mentors will invest 7,5 hours of meetings to support and provide guidance to CSIs for the smooth development of their activities and solving problems that may arise.

Mentorship

The mentors are experts in different aspects of citizen science who will help the CSIs and provide guidance for the correct execution of their activities during the Accelerator.

For each Accelerator period IMPETUS will draw upon a pool of external mentors who will offer specialist expertise to the CSIs. 4 IMPETUS partners will also act as mentors (Science for Change, T6 Ecosystems, Nesta, King's College London).

Mentors selection

The mentors selection will be made as follows:

- **Creation of a pool of potential mentors (February):** IMPETUS partners will collaboratively pool the names of citizen science professionals from their own network of contacts.
- **Questionnaire on expertise (March):** Science for Change will create a questionnaire to assess the level of expertise of the mentors in:
 - a. Different key aspects of citizen science: Citizen engagement, EDI (Equity, Diversity, Inclusivity), Quality data and Open Science (FAIR), Communication strategies & activities, Ethical & legal aspects, Policy Impact, Financial sustainability & funding, Educational strategies & activities.
 - b. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): to evaluate the knowledge in different fields.

This questionnaire is sent to mentors in the pool and also through relevant citizen science mailing lists (e.x. ECSA members and board).

- **Matchmaking exercise (April):** Once the projects from each annual call are selected, Science for Change will carry out a matchmaking exercise, taking into account the following criteria, in the following order:

- a. Only mentors with a medium or high level of expertise in "Citizen engagement" and "EDI" are considered, as these two topics are those that are considered basic for a mentor to provide guidance to any citizen science project.
- b. Matching between the specific needs of the CSIs (expressed or detected during the interview phase in the selection process) and the expertise of the mentors in different aspects of citizen science.
- c. Match between the SDG of the CSIs and the expertise of the mentors in that field.

Mentors roles & responsibilities

Mentors specifically commit to:

- Provide support and advice to CSIs in the drafting of their project documents (during the negotiation phase).
- Advise them for the proper implementation of their activities and for the achievement of their objectives, KPIs and expected impacts (during the Accelerator).
- Provide them with documentation or tools if needed (in general).

The mentors commit to dedicate a **mandatory minimum of:**

- **5,5 hours** for general activities (explained below)
- **9,5 hours** per assigned CSIs on mentoring activities.
- The mentor may be asked for some extra tasks (e.g. the delivery of a training or more mentoring), which he/she can accept at its own convenience.

Mentoring will be appropriately rewarded at an intermediate and final stage each year, after passing the monitoring process.

Mentoring process

During the negotiation phase for CSIs

- **Assignment of CSIs and signing of the contract with IMPETUS:** once the matchmaking is completed, mentors will be informed of their assigned CSIs. Mentors can request changes and Science for

Change will try to reallocate the CSIs as far as possible. Once mentors have agreed to mentor their proposed CSIs, the contract with IMPETUS will be signed.

- **Mentors Welcome webinar (April - 1 hour):** once the matchmaking CSIs-mentors is made, the first task the mentors have to perform is to help the CSI to draft their projects documents. In order for all mentors to share the same criteria, Science for Change will hold a Welcome webinar where the mentors will be provided with the evaluation criteria that IMPETUS will use to evaluate the quality of the documents.
- **Creation of a communication channel between mentors (Slack or similar) (May):** to facilitate the exchange and collaboration between CSIs, IMPETUS consortium will create a dedicated agile communication channel.
- **Bootcamp (May - 1,5 hours):** the mentors are requested to attend the first part of the bootcamp to introduce themselves and to get to know the IMPETUS consortium and the selected CSIs.
- **Work on project documents (deadline June - 2 hours):** from the start of the negotiation phase, CSIs will have approximately 1 month and a half to work on their project documents, with the celebration of the bootcamp taking place in the middle. After the Welcome webinar, the mentors are able to start working with their assigned CSIs. Each mentor is expected to invest 2 hours of mentoring (1 hour before the bootcamp and 1 hour after the bootcamp) for this task.

During the IMPETUS Accelerator (June - December)

During the accelerator, the CSIs have to develop both the implementation activities of their project and the activities necessary to successfully complete their process with IMPETUS.

For this, the mentors are expected to help and guide them through:

- **Monthly update calls with CSIs (7,5 hours):** Taking into account 1 month of summer holidays, CSIs will have to complete 7,5 hours of meetings with their mentor, spread over approximately 1.5 hours per month (5 meetings). This is just a proposal. The decision on how to distribute the 7.5 hours throughout the Accelerator is in the hands of each CSI-mentor. In the case that a CSI-mentor considers it necessary to increase the mentoring hours, this may be done, after consultation and validation by Science for Change. The completion of these meetings will be verified by the IMPETUS consortium through the minutes of the meetings (to be uploaded in Moodle).

The bootcamp

The bootcamp is a one-week course for CSIs to deepen their understanding of different key elements of citizen science and thereby help them to refine their Work Plan for the next 6 months and optionally for their future development beyond IMPETUS.

Objectives and learning outcomes

The objectives of the bootcamp are:

- To provide CSIs with in-depth knowledge on key elements of citizen science.
- To foster debate and reflection
- To promote networking and sharing of knowledge among the CSI and with the IMPETUS team
- To provide support to CSIs in defining their Work Plan

After this bootcamp, the participants will be able to:

- Understand in depth the main topics related to citizen science.
- Identify the short-term project objectives.
- Describe the planned activities to achieve the project objectives.
- Analyse the sustainability and potential risks of their initiative.
- Identify and analyse potential stakeholders to their project.
- Plan engagement strategies to reach their target stakeholders.
- Develop communication strategies for their initiative.
- Assess and evaluate the potential impact of their project.
- Argue and understand the ethics of their initiative.
- Create a final Work Plan for their citizen science project.

Bootcamp details

To accomplish these objectives, the bootcamp is divided as follows:

- **6 topics:** “Impact Assessment”, “EDI (Equity, diversity, inclusivity)”, “engagement strategies”, “Policy”, “communication strategies”, “Quality data and open science, Data Management Plan, Ethics”
- The teachers who teach the topics are partners of the IMPETUS consortium.
- Each topic is divided into a theoretical part and a practical dynamics, using online tools, play books, etc.

- In order to guarantee the correct development of the participatory activities in manageable groups, different breakout rooms will be defined according to the number of participants in each topic. IMPETUS partners will act as facilitators in these rooms.
- Each topic is related to a specific section of the Work Plan + Data & Ethics document
- Specific time slots are devoted to work on the project documents, with the help of the "teachers".
- The timetables have been designed taking into account the work-life balance, as well as the time differences between countries.

The bootcamp will be taught on the Zoom videoconference platform. A member of Science for Change will act as a host during the whole week, while another will be of technical support.

Bootcamp programme 2023

Day 1 - 22nd May 2023

Time (CET)	Topic	Brief description	Speaker
10h -10:30h	Warm Welcome	What's IMPETUS	Gefion Thuermer (KCL)
10:30-11:30h		Ice breaker Speed dating to get to know each other	Diana Reinoso (SFC)
11:30-11:45	<i>Break</i>		
11:45 - 12:30h	Intro CS	What's Citizen Science for IMPETUS Our challenges, our core values	Gefion Thuermer (KCL) & Rosa Arias (SFC)
12:30-13:00h	Impact Assessment (I)	Introduction Theoretical explanation of impact assessment (IA) and why we should do it. CS projects that have an impact: best practices	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
13:00-13:30h		Introduction to the Impact Assessment Canvas Theoretical session on where pilots will be guided through the identification of their areas of impact by filling in the IA canvas	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
13:30-14:15h	<i>Lunch break</i>		
14:15-14:45h	Impact Assessment (II)	Sustainable development goals (SDGs) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI): Theoretical introduction of what they are and why they matter	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
14:45-15:30		Hands-on session: IA canvas Participatory activity to fill the IA canvas and open discussion about the identified areas	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
15:30-15:45h		Saying goodbye Questionary	Diana Reinoso (SFC)

Day 2 - 23rd May 2023

10:00-10:30	EDI – Equity, diversity, inclusivity	Open discussion: What does EDI mean to you?	Aleks Berditchevskaia (NESTA)
10:30-10:45		Theoretical session: why EDI matters in CS	Aleks Berditchevskaia (NESTA)
10:45-11:30		Practical session: EDI audit and peer review	Aleks Berditchevskaia & Alexandra Albert (NESTA)
11:30-11:45	<i>Break</i>		
11:45-12:15	Engagement Strategies	Theoretical introduction of engagement strategies in CS, levels of engagement, 4H and escalator flexibility	Carla Perucca (SFC)
12:15-13:30		Practical session on how to reach the target stakeholders	Carla Perucca (SFC)
13:30-14:15h	<i>Lunch break</i>		
14:15-15:45	Hands-on session: Work Plan 1	Practical work on sections devoted to the specific topics on Day 1 and Day 2	SFC, KCL, T6ECO, NESTA
15:45-16:00		Saying goodbye Questionnaire	

Day 3 - 24th May 2023

10:00-10:45	Policy	Impact for policy Theoretical session and discussion around policy cycle and what impact of policy means.	Aleks Berditchevskaia (NESTA)
10:45-11:45		Interactive session with Create Change Collective Intelligence playbook Practical session to think through different impacts of policy methods and approaches and which approaches might be best suited to different policymakers	Aleks Berditchevskaia (NESTA)
11:45-12:00	<i>Break</i>		
12:00-12:45	Communication Strategies	Theoretical session about why communication is relevance at different stage of the project and what are the element of a good communication	Andrea Troncoso (EUSEA)
12:45-13:30		Theoretical session on basic concept of communication strategies, such as target audiences, messages, innovative tools and impact. indicators.	Joana Magalhães (SFC)
13:30-14:15h	<i>Lunch break</i>		
14:15-15:45	Communication Strategies	Practical co-design session to obtain a communication strategy with and for 4H stakeholders and journalists	Joana Magalhães (SFC)
15:30h - 15:45h		Saying goodbye Questionnaire	Diana Reinoso (SFC)

Day 4 - 25th May 2023

10:00-10:45	Quality data and open science, DMP, Ethics	Theoretical session: why do we work with data, how do we best do it and why does this matter?	Gefion Thuermer (KCL)
10:45-12:00		Practical session where the project will think through the Data&Ethics document. Ethics peer review	Gefion Thuermer (KCL)
12:00-12:15	<i>Break</i>		
12:15-13:15	Impact Assessment (II)	From theory to practice Pilots work with T6 for refining their canvas	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
13:15-13:45		From theory to practice Theoretical session about how to gather the data you need	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
13:45-14:30	<i>Lunch break</i>		
14:30-15:00	Impact Assessment (II)	From theory to practice Open Discussion & Q&A	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
15:00-16:00	Hands-on session: Work Plan 2	Practical work on sections devoted to the specific topics on Day 3 and Day 4	SFC, KCL, T6ECO, NESTA, EUSEA
16:00-16:15		Saying goodbye	

Day 5 - 26th May 2023

10:00h - 11:30h	Impact Assessment (III)	From Impact Assessment Canvas to data gathering process: developing a data gathering plan	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
11:30h - 12:00h		Practical session to develop a data gathering plan from IA canvas	
12:00h - 12:15h		Final remarks and Q&A session	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
12:00h - 12:15h		<i>Break</i>	
12:15h - 12:45h	Warm Goodbye	Wrap up + questionnaire next steps, timeline to launch, etc.	IMPETUS consortium partners

Accelerator trainings & aperitives

As explained above, once the Accelerator officially starts, CSIs will be provided with three things:

- a training program, focused on the specific knowledge and skills needs of each cohort.
- aperitives where the CSIs will have mutual-learning opportunities within and between cohorts through the IMPETUS Aperitives.

Rationale behind the training program

IMPETUS wants to keep a tailor-made perspective in the development of the training programme. Therefore, from the initial battery of potential trainings to be delivered (detailed below), the most appropriate ones will be chosen each year, depending on the needs and knowledge gaps expressed by each cohort of CSIs in the pre-questionnaire. In addition, mentors or other external experts may be requested to deliver other specific training sessions.

Throughout each Accelerator, 5 training sessions (1.5 hours each) will be delivered in approximately 1 session per month (June-July and September-November).

Initial battery of possible trainings

Topic	Partner
Building newsworthy stories from citizen generated data with data journalists	EUSEA, SfC
Use data in service of society, and increasing public trust in science	SfC, Nesta
Data science primer, including data discovery, FAIR publication, cleaning, visualizations	KCL
Boost creativity through collaboration with artists	AE, KCL
Incorporating a gender dimension in CSI	SfC
Increase engagement of quadruple helix stakeholders using the NEWSERA methodology	SfC
Informing evidence-based policies	Nesta

Co-creating business plan models for projects' scalability and replicability	T6
Financial sustainability	T6
Advocacy, policy engagement, and strategic influencing	Nesta, T6

IMPETUS Aperitives

The objective of the IMPETUS Aperitives is to foster connections and mutual learning within and between pilot cohorts. Additionally, IMPETUS will create bridges with other external communities such as national and international CSIs in their own field of research or similar, as well as connection with the winning consortium from topic ERA-60, EU-Citizen.Science, CS Observatories, etc., leveraging the IMPETUS partners' connections to these networks.

During each Accelerator, 2 aperitives will be held (1,5 hours each). Their specific definition, as in the case of the trainings, will be tailor-made, depending on the characteristics of each cohort.

Monitoring procedure

In IMPETUS, both the performance of the CSIs and mentors are going to be monitored.

The monitoring procedure for CSIs (September & December)

To keep track of the smooth running of the CSIs' activities within the Accelerator, IMPETUS will follow a monitoring procedure. This procedure aims to assess that the activities are developing correctly as agreed in the contract and to provide help or guidance if necessary.

To qualify for the funding in totality, participants must complete all of the activities outlined below:

- **Attend the Accelerator trainings:**
 - Kickstarting projects have to attend a minimum of 3 out of 5.
 - Sustaining projects have to attend a minimum of 2.
- **Attend the Aperitives:** All CSIs have to attend a minimum of 1 out of 2.
- **Attend monthly update calls with mentors:** CSIs have to complete 7,5 hours of meetings with their mentor, spread over approximately 1.5 hours per month (5 meetings). The completion of these meetings will be verified by the IMPETUS consortium through the minutes of the meetings (to be uploaded in Moodle).
- **Participate in IMPETUS impact assessment activities,** such as:
 - Send at least one survey to their citizen scientists (or organize another process for data gathering from them).
 - Compile a qualitative-quantitative impact assessment report following the methodology described in the IMPETUS training (December).
 - Answer a post-questionnaire on Accelerator achievements (December).
- **Participate in IMPETUS communication and dissemination efforts,** such as:
 - Provide a picture and a text to be shared on the IMPETUS website and social media channels (June).
 - Provide a short video about their work (December).
 - Present their project at events when possible – all projects should allocate a portion of their budget to outreach activities.
 - Acknowledge IMPETUS funding, and conduct outreach activities about IMPETUS to your network.

They will be provided with IMPETUS visual materials to perform these activities.

In addition to carrying out the activities mentioned above, to access the second Accelerator payment the CSIs will have to:

- **Provide a formal report outlining their activities at the mid-term point and end of the project (September & December).** With it IMPETUS intend to verify that they have effectively carried out the activities planned in the Work Plan + Data & Ethics document. Any deviation from the original plan must be duly justified.
- **Attend an interview with and provide feedback to the IMPETUS team (December)**

Summary of mandatory activities for CSIs during the Accelerator Programme

	Kickstarting projects	Sustaining projects
Attend the Accelerator trainings	3 out of 5	2 out of 5
Attend the Aperitives	1 out of 2	
Attend monthly update calls with mentors	7.5 hours (possible extension after consultation and validation by Science for Change)	
Develop activities agreed on the Work Plan + Data & Ethics document	Deviations should be justified	
Participate in IMPETUS impact assessment activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One survey to their citizen scientists (or another process) • Quali-quantitative impact assessment report (December). • Post-questionnaire on Accelerator achievements (December) 	
Participate in IMPETUS communication and dissemination efforts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pictures + text (June) • Short video about (December) • Present their project at events • Acknowledge IMPETUS funding 	
Participate in the monitoring procedure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal report (September & December) • Attend an interview (December) 	

Once the monitoring process has been completed and IMPETUS have positively evaluated the completion of their project, the second payment will be made.

The monitoring procedure for mentors (July & October & December)

To keep track of the smooth running of the mentoring activities within the Accelerator, Science for Change will follow a monitoring procedure. This procedure aims to assess that the activities are being developed according to the contract and to provide the mentors with help or guidance if necessary.

The procedure will consist of the following:

- **3 collective meetings with all the mentors (July - October - December/ 1 hour each):** throughout the Accelerator, 3 collective meetings are held to share experiences, doubts and needs between the mentors and the IMPETUS consortium. The third meeting will be specifically devoted to assess the mentoring process.
- **Objective measures:** to evaluate both quantitatively and qualitatively the performance of the mentors, Science for Change carries out two evaluation periods (September and December), which will also be associated with two payments. The evaluation of mentors is based on:
 - quantitatively: the hours invested, which will be reflected in the minutes of the CSI-mentor meetings (uploaded in Moodle).
 - qualitatively: the result of the mid-term report and the final report of the CSIs.
- **Mentoring evaluation questionnaire (December):** to help IMPETUS assess the mentoring process and introduce improvements for the following years, the mentors will be asked to fill in a final questionnaire..

The IMPETUS consortium reserves the right at any time to dispense with a mentor in the event that their performance is not adequate. However, in any case, the mentor will be paid for the hours invested up to that date.

Summary of activities for mentors during the Negotiation phase and the Accelerator Programme

Activity	Hours
Attend the webinar	1
Work on Work Plan (I)	1 per CSI
Work on Work Plan (II)	1 per CSI
Extra CSIs reserve list (if applicable)	2 per CSI
Bootcamp	1,5

Monthly meetings	7,5 per CSI
Extra mentoring hours	?
Extra activities (e. g. trainings)	?
Collective meetings (3)	3

Accelerator assessment

The impact of the Accelerator programme, including the training provided during the bootcamp, will be assessed through a series of questionnaires that all CSIs are supposed to fill in at different stages of the programme. It is important to specify that these questionnaires will be anonymous, and they will be filled in individually by each participant. However, the assessment of the Accelerator programme, besides providing a general overview about the impact of the training sessions at the aggregated level, aims to map the “journey” of each participant. In order to do that, all respondents will be asked to indicate a nickname to keep track of their progress (the nickname should be the same in all questionnaires), and, at the same time, preserve the anonymity of their responses.

Specifically, four kinds of evaluation questionnaires have been developed to be delivered to CSIs at four different stages.

- **Pre-bootcamp questionnaire:** this questionnaire has been already mentioned earlier in the document as one of the mandatory steps the CSIs have to complete to pass the negotiation phase. In more detail, it aims to identify knowledge gaps and needs at the individual level to develop more tailored training sessions. The questionnaire is articulated in three different sections. First, a self-assessment about key competences that participants are supposed to develop during the bootcamp and Accelerator programme, namely:
 - set up a communication plan,
 - engage media practitioners,
 - build appealing stories from project results/activities,
 - acknowledge the principles and good practices of Open Science,
 - set up and implement a data management plan,
 - be aware of data justice and implement it,
 - acknowledge the principles of citizen engagement,
 - facilitate social inclusion and diversity in CS activities,
 - map and engage different stakeholders,
 - engage policy-makers and influence related policies and strategies,
 - assess the impact of a CS project,
 - be familiar with the SDG targets and indicators as well as the New Green Deal policy,

- comply with ethical aspects related to research and engagement processes, and
- make a CS project scalable and financially sustainable in the long run.

Second, respondents are asked to indicate what they would like to learn during the Accelerator and which skills they would like to acquire or further develop. Finally, this questionnaire aims to map their expectations about the mentoring programme, and if there are specific topics they will need more support.

- **Post-bootcamp questionnaire:** this questionnaire aims to map the impact of the bootcamp training sessions on skill acquisition. To this aim, we will evaluate if participants increased their knowledge on the key competences they were asked to self-assess in the pre-bootcamp questionnaire (with the exception of financial sustainability and scalability since these trainings will be specifically developed during the Accelerator). Furthermore, it will be assessed an eventual increase in their interest towards the main topics of the bootcamp, i.e., communication strategies, open science, data justice, citizen engagement, inclusivity and diversity, stakeholder engagement, advocacy and policy dialogue, impact assessment, SDGs and Green Deal policies, and Ethics of research. Finally, general feedback about what they liked and what it is possible to improve will be collected to enhance the contribution of the bootcamp for the following cohorts.
- **Post-training session questionnaire:** a very short survey will be delivered to participants at the end of each training session within the Accelerator programme to gather feedback on the specific training sessions they attended. Specifically, they will be asked whether they found the training useful, what they liked and what it is possible to improve, so that future training sessions will be adjusted accordingly.
- **Post-accelerator questionnaire:** this questionnaire aims to map the overall impact of the Accelerator programme, and it will be delivered at the end of the Accelerator (december). The extent is the same as the post-bootcamp questionnaire, integrating questions on key competences and interest with the topic of financial sustainability and scalability. Moreover, participants will be asked to point out whether what they learned during the training sessions was effectively implemented within their project, and in which way it will influence their current and future works. Finally, respondents are expected to provide final feedback on the mentoring programme.

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